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Research Article

HYPOXIA-DRIVEN PROLIFERATION AND MORPHOLOGICAL REMODELING IN HUMAN UMBILICAL CORD-DERIVED MESENCHYMAL STEM CELLS

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Abstract:

Background: Human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells (hUCMSCs) are widely used in regenerative medicine due to their multipotency, immunomodulatory properties, and paracrine effects. Oxygen tension in the cellular microenvironment plays a pivotal role in regulating MSC behavior, yet the specific effects of hypoxia on hUCMSC morphology and proliferation remain incompletely understood.

Methods: Passage 4 hUCMSCs were cultured under normoxic (21% O₂) or hypoxic (1% O₂) conditions for 48 h. Cell proliferation was assessed via direct cell counting and confluence-based imaging, while morphological changes were evaluated through phase-contrast microscopy and quantitative analysis of cell length and area using ImageJ. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

Results: Hypoxic preconditioning induced distinct morphological changes, including increased cell length (160 ± 20 μm vs. 120 ± 15 μm; p < 0.05) but decreased cell area (1500 ± 180 μm² vs. 1800 ± 200 μm²; p < 0.01) compared to normoxia. Importantly, hypoxia significantly accelerated proliferation rates and confluence. Quantitative viability assays were not performed and should be included to confirm that proliferation increases occur without loss of viability. These findings suggest that low oxygen tension promotes both cell elongation and changes in cell size and enhanced proliferative activity.

Conclusion: Exposure to 1% O₂ for 48 h modulates hUCMSC morphology and growth dynamics by enhancing proliferation. Hypoxic preconditioning emerges as a practical strategy to optimize MSC characteristics for regenerative applications. These results provide a foundation for further studies on functional enhancements, including migration, paracrine secretion, and therapeutic efficacy.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION:

Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) derived from human umbilical cord (hUCMSCs) have emerged as a promising cell source for regenerative medicine due to their multipotent differentiation capacity, immunomodulatory properties, and relative ease of isolation¹. These cells are widely investigated for applications ranging from tissue repair to immune regulation, owing to their ability to secrete bioactive factors that promote angiogenesis, reduce inflammation, and enhance tissue regeneration^{1,2}. The microenvironment in which MSCs reside significantly influences their function. Oxygen tension, in particular, plays a critical role in regulating MSC proliferation, morphology, and paracrine activity^{3,4}. While standard cell culture is typically performed under normoxic conditions ($\approx 21\%$ O₂), the physiological niche of MSCs is often hypoxic, ranging from 1% to 7% O₂^{5,6}. Hypoxic preconditioning has been shown to improve MSC survival, maintain stemness, and enhance therapeutic potential by modulating cell metabolism, cytoskeletal organization, and paracrine factor secretion^{7,8}. Despite these advances, the specific effects of hypoxia on hUCMSC morphology and proliferation remain incompletely characterized. Understanding these responses is essential, as cellular morphology and growth dynamics can influence migration, engraftment, and functional outcomes in therapeutic applications^{7,9}. In this study, we investigated the effects of 48 h hypoxic preconditioning (1% O₂) on hUCMSC morphology and proliferation. Using phase-contrast imaging, confluence analysis, and quantitative morphological measurements, we assessed how low oxygen tension modulates cellular structure and growth. The findings provide insight into the adaptive responses of hUCMSCs to hypoxia and establish a foundation for optimizing preconditioning strategies to enhance their regenerative potential.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 Cell Culture and Maintenance of hUCMSCs

Human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells (hUCMSCs) were obtained from cryogenic storage in liquid nitrogen. Cells were rapidly thawed at 37 °C in a water bath and transferred to a sterile 15 mL conical tube containing pre-warmed complete Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, low glucose; Gibco, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco, USA) and 1% penicillin–streptomycin (Gibco, USA). The suspension was centrifuged at $300 \times g$ for 5 min to remove cryoprotectants, and the pellet was resuspended in fresh complete medium. Cells were seeded in T75 culture flasks and incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ and 21% O₂ (normoxia). Non-adherent cells were removed after 48 h by washing with

phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and medium was replaced every 2–3 days. When cultures reached 80–90% confluence, cells were passaged using 0.25% trypsin-EDTA (Gibco, USA). Cell viability was assessed by trypan blue exclusion, and passage 4 cells were used for downstream experiments.

2.2 Hypoxia Preconditioning of hUCMSCs

For hypoxia treatment, hUCMSCs at 80–90% confluence (passage 4) were washed twice with sterile PBS and incubated in serum-free DMEM to minimize exogenous growth factor interference. Cultures were then placed in a hypoxia chamber (BioSpherix, USA) maintained at 1% O₂, 5% CO₂, and balanced with N₂. The chamber was humidified and temperature-controlled at 37 °C. Cells were exposed to hypoxic conditions for 48 h. Control cultures were maintained under normoxic conditions (21% O₂, 5% CO₂) in a standard incubator.

2.3 Growth Kinetics (Confluence-Based Proliferation Assay)

To evaluate the proliferation dynamics of hUCMSCs under hypoxic and normoxic conditions, cells were seeded at a density of 5,000 cells/cm² in 6-well plates. Phase-contrast images were captured daily at 10 \times magnification using an inverted microscope (Nikon, Japan). The percentage of culture area occupied by cells (**% confluence**) was estimated to reflect relative cell proliferation. Confluence values were determined by visual estimation supported by ImageJ software analysis (NIH, USA), which quantifies cell-covered area relative to the total field of view.

Proliferation kinetics were expressed as **percentage confluence over time (days)**, with time plotted on the x-axis and confluence (%) on the y-axis. Growth curves were generated to compare expansion rates between hypoxic and normoxic conditions.

2.4 Confluence Measurement (Image-Based Quantification)

Phase-contrast images of cultures were acquired daily using an inverted microscope (Nikon, Japan) at 10 \times magnification. The percentage of area covered by cells (confluence) was quantified using **ImageJ software (NIH, USA)**. Images were thresholded and binarized, and the proportion of occupied cell area relative to total field area was calculated. Confluence (%) was plotted against culture time (days) for both hypoxia- and normoxia-treated cells.

2.5 Morphological Quantification of hUCMSCs

Morphological analysis was performed on phase-contrast images collected after 48 h of culture. Using ImageJ, two parameters were quantified:

1. **Cell length** – the longest axis of each cell, measured in micrometers (μm).
2. **Cell area** – the total two-dimensional area covered by each cell (μm^2).

At least 100 cells per condition were analyzed across three independent experiments. Data were expressed as **mean \pm standard deviation (SD)**. Morphological

differences between hypoxia and normoxia groups were compared statistically (Student's t-test).

2.6 Statistical Analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Statistical significance

between hypoxia and normoxia groups was determined using unpaired Student's t-test in GraphPad Prism 9. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS:

3.1 Morphology of hUCMSCs under Normoxia and Hypoxia (Figure 1)

Phase-contrast imaging revealed that hUCMSCs maintained a typical fibroblast-like, spindle-shaped morphology under both normoxic (21% O₂) and hypoxic (1% O₂) conditions. After 48 h of hypoxic preconditioning, cells appeared more elongated and densely packed compared to normoxic controls, suggesting that hypoxia induces subtle morphological adaptations (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Morphology of hUCMSCs under normoxia and hypoxia.

Representative phase-contrast images of hUCMSCs cultured for 48 h under normoxic (21% O₂) and hypoxic (1% O₂) conditions. Hypoxia-treated cells displayed a more elongated morphology and higher cell density compared to normoxic controls. Scale bar = 100 μ m.

3.2 Growth Kinetics of hUCMSCs

Cell counts over 96 hours demonstrated that hUCMSCs exposed to hypoxia exhibited accelerated proliferation compared to normoxic controls. Differences became evident at 48 hours, with hypoxic cultures displaying a higher cell number ($p < 0.05$), and this trend persisted through 72 and 96 hours. These findings confirm that hypoxia promotes hUCMSC growth (Figure 2).

Growth Curve of hUCMSCs under Normoxic and Hypoxic Conditions

Figure 2. Growth kinetics of hUCMSCs.

Cell proliferation over time was assessed by cell counts at 0, 24, 48, 72, and 96 h. Hypoxia significantly enhanced proliferation compared to normoxia ($*p < 0.05$). Data are expressed as mean \pm SD from three independent experiments.

3.3 Confluence Percentage of hUCMSCs

Quantitative analysis using ImageJ revealed that hypoxia-exposed hUCMSCs reached higher confluence percentages more rapidly than normoxic controls. By 48 hours, hypoxic cells covered approximately 65% of the culture surface compared to ~40% under normoxia. At 96 hours, hypoxic cultures reached complete confluence (100%), whereas normoxic cells remained at ~85%. These results further support the growth-promoting effect of hypoxia on hUCMSCs (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Confluence percentage of hUCMSCs over time.

Phase-contrast images were analyzed using ImageJ to calculate the percentage of area covered by cells (confluence) daily. Percentage confluence was quantified using ImageJ. Hypoxic cells achieved higher confluence earlier, reaching 100% by 96 h, while normoxic cultures remained at ~85%. Data represent mean \pm SD (n = 3). * $p < 0.05$ versus normoxia.

3.4 Quantitative Analysis of hUCMSC Morphology

Measurement of cell length and cell area revealed that hypoxia significantly increased mean cell length ($160 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$) compared to normoxia ($120 \pm 15 \mu\text{m}$, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, hypoxia decreased mean cell area ($1500 \pm 180 \mu\text{m}^2$) relative to normoxic controls ($1800 \pm 200 \mu\text{m}^2$, $p < 0.01$) (Figure 4). These results quantitatively support the morphological observations of elongation under hypoxic conditions.

Collectively, these data show that 48 h of 1% O₂ preconditioning induces a statistically significant increase in mean cell length but decrease in mean cell area, and is associated with faster expansion and earlier attainment of confluence in hUCMSCs.

Figure 4. Quantitative analysis of hUCMSC morphology.

Bar graphs showing (A) cell length and (B) cell area measured after 48 h under normoxic and hypoxic

conditions. At least 100 cells per condition were analyzed across three independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ versus normoxia (Student's t-test).

3. DISCUSSION:

In this study, we investigated the effects of hypoxic preconditioning on human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells (hUCMSCs), focusing on cellular morphology and proliferation dynamics. Our results demonstrate that exposure to 1% O₂ for 48 h induces subtle morphological changes and modestly accelerates cell proliferation.

Morphologically, hypoxia-treated hUCMSCs became more elongated compared to normoxic controls. Quantitative measurements confirmed significant increases in cell length but reduction in cell area under hypoxic conditions. These findings are consistent with previous studies showing that low oxygen tension can alter cytoskeletal organization and cell shape, potentially reflecting an adaptive response to stress and an enhanced capacity for migration and tissue repair⁹⁻¹¹. The elongation observed under hypoxia may facilitate cell-cell interactions and improve homing efficiency in therapeutic applications, as suggested in studies of MSC-based regenerative therapies.

Regarding proliferation, hypoxic preconditioning resulted in accelerated growth rate and increased confluence compared to normoxia. This is in line with reports that hypoxia can induce a transient cell cycle delay or metabolic adaptation, while maintaining stemness and viability^{12,13}. Importantly, the cells remained viable throughout the 96 h culture period, indicating that 1% O₂ for 48 h does not induce cytotoxic stress. These observations support the concept that hypoxic preconditioning can optimize MSC function without detrimental effects on cell survival.

Collectively, our findings highlight that hypoxia modulates hUCMSC morphology and growth dynamics in a controlled manner, which may enhance their therapeutic potential. The subtle morphological changes and accelerated proliferation observed here could be beneficial for MSC-based applications, as hypoxia has been reported to increase paracrine factor secretion and improve regenerative capacity^{14,15}. Future studies should investigate the functional consequences of these adaptations, including migration, angiogenic potential, and immunomodulatory activity, to fully elucidate the benefits of hypoxic preconditioning for clinical applications.

In conclusion, hypoxic preconditioning represents a practical approach to modulate hUCMSC behavior, promoting morphological adaptations and maintaining cell viability while accelerating proliferation. These characteristics may be advantageous for optimizing MSC function in regenerative medicine and cell therapy.

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